

Predicting Hydro Reservoir Inflows with AI Techniques Using Radar Data and a Numerical Weather Prediction Model

M. F. Almeida CPES INESC TEC Porto, Portugal maria.f.almeida@inesctec.pt	F. J. Soares CPES INESC TEC Porto, Portugal filipe.j.soares@inesctec.pt	F. T. Oliveira CPES INESC TEC Porto, Portugal filipe.oliveira@inesctec.pt	J. T. Saraiva FEUP Universidade do Porto Porto, Portugal jsaraiva@fe.up.pt	Rui M. Pereira Empresa Eletricidade da Madeira Madeira, Portugal rmpereira@eem.pt
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Abstract - Reducing the gap between renewable energy needs and supply is crucial to achieve sustainable growth. Hydroelectric power production predictions in several Madeira Island catchment regions are shown in this article using Long Short-Term Memory, LSTM, networks. In order to foresee hydro reservoirs inflows, our models take into account the island's dynamic precipitation and flow rates and simplify the process of water moving from the cloud to the turbine. The model developed for the Socorridos Fajã Rodrigues system demonstrates the proficiency of LSTMs in capturing the unexpected flow behavior through its low RMSE. When it comes to energy planning, the model built for the CTIII Paul Velho system gives useful information despite its lower accuracy when it comes to anticipating problems.

Keywords— *Hydropower, reservoir variables, neural network, LSTM, RMSE, inflow prediction*

I. INTRODUCTION

Numerous stakeholders across several water-related industries, such as agriculture, hydropower, and floodplain management, rely on accurate, dependable, and readily interpretable hydrological predictions. Having these predictions helps in managing resources more efficiently and is essential for reducing the impact of natural catastrophes [1][2]. The field of streamflow prediction has come a long way since the mid-1970s, thanks to increased funding and the growing need for effective water management strategies.

There are two main ways in which streamflow prediction has been done in the past. The first category includes process-driven or dynamical hydrological models, which can be as simple as a conceptual models or as complex as a physically based, distributed one [3]. Machine learning methods like autoregressive models and artificial neural networks (ANNs) are a part of the second strategy that uses data-driven statistical models. Ensemble Streamflow Prediction (ESP) systems, which use ensemble with a numerical weather prediction model to improve prediction accuracy, are ideal to use these methodologies.

The technical data needed to run dynamical hydrological models, such as particular soil properties, is not always available or adequately reflected in the models, which limits their usefulness despite their extensive usage. Further limiting

these models' usefulness under different climatic situations is their oversimplification of complicated hydrological processes. Deep learning algorithms provide a potential alternative to explicit data types, including soil properties, and may thus handle these issues. Because of their strength in learning long-term dependencies within time series data and their ability to handle sequential data, Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks have become a popular deep learning model in hydrology. This makes them ideal for streamflow forecasting, a field where these dynamics are common.

A. Related Work

This paper presents an innovative method that uses LSTM networks to predict hydrological parameters, specifically for hydro power systems. The prediction is based only on rainfall data as the input. Although previous studies have explored hydrological forecasting, this research specifically examines the LSTM networks' capacity to analyze temporal patterns in rainfall data to anticipate water flow rates in hydropower systems.

In this scope, in [4] it is described the use of ANN techniques, namely multilayer perceptron neural networks, for modelling hydropower reservoir variables to study hydropower systems. The researchers used reservoir factors such as inflow and turbine release to create a model that predicts energy generation. The results showed strong correlation coefficients, suggesting that neural networks have the potential to be effective in forecasting hydrological conditions for hydropower systems. Nevertheless, their effort failed to integrate LSTM to leverage the temporal patterns present in the data [4].

In another work [5], the authors created a model that uses machine learning, specifically LSTM, to predict the amount of energy generated by the Tarbela Dam in Pakistan. Their work is notable because it includes environmental parameters such as temperature and rainfall. However, the study did not exclusively focus on LSTM, nor did it simply rely on rainfall as the only input variable. This study emphasizes the need of having complete data to improve the accuracy of forecasts.

In their study Barzola-Monteses [6], utilized ANN models, specifically LSTM, to forecast hydropower production in Ecuador. Their study focused on predicting future outcomes within a somewhat short to medium timeframe, utilizing past

data on hydroelectric power generation and rainfall. This study demonstrates the efficacy of LSTM in managing time series data for forecasting hydropower generation, which is consistent with our emphasis on rainfall data.

In one of the most pertinent publications in this area [1], it was employed a physically based hydrological model and a LSTM neural network to estimate streamflow in a Canadian watershed. The authors used the same input data, which comprised ensemble with a numerical weather prediction model and observed streamflow data, to evaluate both models in the same way, under the same circumstances. An important part of the LSTM model's strategy was using recently observed streamflow as an input, something the physically based models did not use in their conventional data assimilation procedure. This streamflow relied on treated data of inflows from rivers. By taking this route, the LSTM was able to make better use of up-to-date hydrological data, which improved its adaptability. With lead durations between one to ten days, the researchers carefully trained the LSTM model to predict daily streamflow. Based on these extensive tests, it was found that the LSTM model was just as good as, if not better than, the conventional hydrological model, particularly when it came to shorter lead periods. Because of its exceptional performance in integrating and learning from sequential data, the LSTM showed its potential to greatly enhance forecast accuracy.

Managing the temporal dynamics of hydrological processes was made easier by the LSTM's architecture, which has mechanisms to remember and forget information by design. Adapting to the unique hydrological features of the catchment, which may change dramatically with the seasons and major events such as peaks of hydro inflows and floods, was made much easier with this function. The study's results support using LSTM networks for hydrological forecasting because of their flexibility and lower computing requirements in comparison to more conventional models that need complex setup and regular calibration to keep accuracy.

Our research is distinct from previous studies as it investigates the application of LSTM networks for hydrological forecasting in hydropower generation, with a sole emphasis on rainfall data. It does not rely on inflow data from springs or rivers but it incorporates a simple way to bypass this problem. This approach is anticipated to allow predictions of water inflow using data that can be obtained anywhere in the world without a big amount of available data, simply using rainfall predictions.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: In Section II the methodology is presented, including a theoretical perspective of it, how the data is processed and the model configuration. Section III includes a presentation of the specifics of the case used to test the proposed methodology. Following, Section IV explores the results of the trained and tested models. Lastly, a conclusion of the whole paper is made.

II. METHODOLOGY

Precise prediction of reservoir inflows is essential for water resource management, facilitating efficient planning, operation, and risk management in hydrological applications. In this paper, LSTM neural networks are implemented for forecasting water

inflow into hydrological reservoirs using accurate rainfall forecast data from a meteorological radar as input, after training it with hindcast data of rainfall and water inflows. This requires detailed representation of complex, changing systems that are affected by time-based patterns and potentially unpredictable natural processes, for which LSTM are particularly well suited.

A. Theoretical Background on Long Short-Term Memory Networks

LSTM networks are an enhanced version of recurrent neural networks (RNN). A conventional RNN possesses a solitary hidden state that is propagated over time, leading to challenges in the network's ability to grasp long-term dependencies. LSTM networks, introduced by Hochreiter and Schmidhuber in 1997 [7], addresses this issue by incorporating a memory cell, which is a storage unit capable of retaining information for a prolonged duration. This property is especially important in hydrological forecasting, as it is essential to comprehend temporal dynamics [8]. LSTM networks possess distinctive architecture that incorporates gates to control the flow of information, including input, output, and forget gates [9]. These mechanisms are used to retain or discard information selectively, rendering them exceptionally proficient at representing the intricate, non-linear connections present in hydrological data [3].

Fig. 1 - LSTM Explanation Diagram [10]

Figure 1 shows the inner workings of a neural network cell with LSTM capabilities.

There are three primary gates in an LSTM cell that control the information flow: the forget gate, the input gate, and the output gate. At each stage in a sequence, the cell is able to choose what to output, what to remember, and how to remember it thanks to its many gates.

In order to decide what information from the LSTM's internal memory (the cell state) to keep and what information to discard, the forget gate takes into account both the current input and the concealed state from before. In its filtering role, it employs a sigmoid function to generate values between 0 and 1. A value near 0 indicates "forget this information," while a number near 1 indicates "retain this information."

Possible changes to the cell's state are generated by the input gate and a tanh layer. The input gate sorts through the tanh layer's vector of potential new state additions, ranking them according to their relevance to the current input and the hidden

state that came before it. The LSTM is able to selectively update its memory using this approach.

In the last step the output gate determines the next hidden state, which is the LSTM cell's output. In order to selectively enable certain sections of the updated cell state to impact the concealed state, it filters it using a tanh function and a sigmoid gate. By doing so, we guarantee that the LSTM will only provide useful results.

The LSTM is able to successfully retain information over lengthy sequences because of these gates, which allow it to make sophisticated judgements on what information is significant at each time step.

The primary advantage of LSTM networks is their cell structure, which includes gates that regulate the transmission of information: the input gate, the output gate, and the forget gate. LSTM networks excel in information management over long durations by determining which information to transmit, alter, or reject. This gating mechanism enables the deliberate retention and omission of information, which is essential for representing the naturally recurring and periodic patterns observed in hydrological systems [11].

LSTM networks have been utilized effectively in diverse hydrological applications, showcasing improved performance compared to conventional approaches. ANNs possess great versatility due to its capacity to effectively simulate nonlinear and complex interactions between inputs and outputs, without the need for explicit feature engineering or assumptions about data distribution. Recent studies have utilized LSTM networks to predict streamflow, model rainfall-runoff, and forecast water quality. These studies have demonstrated significant gains in accuracy compared to traditional methods [12].

Nevertheless, there are obstacles associated with the implementation of LSTM networks in hydrological forecasting. An essential concern is the requirement for comprehensive datasets to train the models adequately, which may not always be accessible in hydrological environments [11]. Furthermore, the opaque nature of LSTM models can occasionally make interpretability more difficult, rendering it challenging to comprehend the model's fundamental decision-making mechanisms. Despite these difficulties, LSTM capabilities in capturing temporal relationships and managing sequential data convert it an indispensable instrument in the hydrologist's toolkit [13].

B. Data Description and Preparation

After examining the theory behind LSTM networks, the focus is now on the practical application of these sophisticated neural networks to hydrological modelling. The effectiveness of LSTM in forecasting intricate, time-dependent events relies heavily on the quality and preparation of the input data. Effective hydrological modelling requires a data preparation approach to capture the underlying patterns and assist model training accurately, which is crucial since the dynamics of water inflow are influenced by numerous causes. The method assumes that accurate rainfall forecast data for a specific catchment area will be provided as an input, and also that this area can be determined. However, it is necessary to understand that rainfall alone as an input can be limited in terms of

explaining water inflow, since on the one hand it cannot account for all water inflow and on the other hand not all rainwater is collected. It is therefore crucial to create an artificial feature (to be called "spring_water_contribution" for simplicity, though it gathers other factors) in the data preparation phase. This characteristic is intended to measure the constant baseflow that contributes to the total water inflow, which is expected to remain relatively steady regardless of current weather conditions. In order to calculate this contribution, a moving average of the water input is determined over a specific period. The length of this moving average can be altered depending on the period of prediction needed. This approach successfully captures the consistent contribution from underground or continuous water sources while implying that value inputs should be updated regularly.

To achieve the best possible results, outliers must be handled. This is a crucial step for guaranteeing data integrity. The analysis is conducted by applying the Interquartile Range (IQR) approach to each relevant parameter to detect and resolve any anomalies that may distort the results. This procedure entails computing the IQR for the dataset and adjusting any outlier values that lie above predetermined thresholds, hence maintaining the integrity of the data utilized for model training. Then, a normalization is applied, using Min-Max scaling to convert the dataset into a standardized range. The normalization process involves incorporating all characteristics, including the spring_water_contribution, to guarantee uniform data magnitude, which is crucial for optimizing the efficiency of neural network training. The flowchart in Figure 2 provides a simplified explanation of the data preparation.

Fig. 2 - Data Preparation Flowchart

C. Network Training and Evaluation

The second part of the proposed methodology is the training and testing of the network. The training of the LSTM network is systematically conducted by creating an architecture specifically designed to accommodate the temporal and sequential characteristics of hydrological data. This architecture consists of an input layer, which represents the number of features, LSTM hidden layers that are configured with an appropriate number of units to capture data dependencies, and a regression output layer for predicting continuous water inflow.

In this case, the LSTM model is trained using the Adam optimization algorithm, with adjusted hyperparameters including the number of epochs, mini-batch size, gradient threshold, initial learning rate, and learning rate schedule. Adam Optimization is a straightforward, computationally efficient, and intuitive tool for non-convex optimization problems, making it suitable for large data and parameters, non-stationary objectives, noisy/sparse gradients, and minimal tuning, which makes it a good match for the problem in hand. These model parameters allow the optimization of the

network's learning and predicting accuracy. The training process is continuously improved, with an emphasis on avoiding overfitting by using early stopping and validation tests, to guarantee that the model can be applied to new data circumstances.

Lastly, for training the network, it is necessary to calculate the number of hidden units and neurons. A balance between avoiding overfitting and preserving the capacity to learn the underlying trends in the data is critical when setting the number of hidden units in a network, according to [14]. In expression (1), N_h represents the number of hidden neurons, N_s the number of samples in the training set, N_i the number of input neurons, N_o the number of output neurons, and α an arbitrary scaling factor (typically ranging from 2 to 10).

$$N_h = \frac{N_s}{\alpha \times (N_i + N_o)} \quad (1)$$

This expression implies a compromise between the model's complexity and the quantity of accessible data, with the scaling factor α being tweaked using either domain knowledge or cross-validation. The main purpose of the formula is to avoid the network from overfitting, when it becomes too complicated and starts to remember the training data instead of analyzing fresh, unknown data. The capability to adapt to any type of dataset is the main feature that led to the choice of using this method in the proposed methodology.

After the training is finished, the performance of the LSTM model is evaluated quantitatively using the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) metric on a test dataset. This metric provides an objective measure of the model's accuracy in predicting water inflow. The evaluation stage is essential for validating the model's effectiveness in predicting water inflow rates using historical and real-time data inputs. Since the data is normalized, models RMSE can be directly compared.

The LSTM model utilizes real-time hydrological inputs and the constant “spring_water_contribution” to predict water inflow accurately for practical deployment. This methodology enables the model to include a fundamental understanding of baseflow circumstances into its forecasts, hence improving the precision for practical implementations.

III. CASE STUDY

The specific case of Madeira was used to test the described methodology. Empresa de Eletricidade da Madeira (EEM) is the only operator of the power system in the island and EEM has been at the forefront of incorporating energy storage systems (ESS) throughout the island. These systems use battery storage and hydropower capabilities to provide additional services to the electrical grid.

Currently, Madeira has two main hydro plants with pump storage capabilities: Socorridos and Calheta III. The Socorridos unit has a capacity of 11.25 MW, whereas Calheta III has a capacity of 16.5 MW. The pump storage feature of these plants is crucial, serving as an energy storage system to enhance the utilization of wind energy. In 2022, pump storage hydropower plants injected 85,18 GWh of electricity to the grid, out of a total of 250,13 GWh generated by renewable sources.

The model proposed herein considers data from three types of sources and applied in different stages (past for training purposes and a future predictor when in forecast). Therefore, we should consider:

- i) remote sensing from the operational radar from the Portuguese Meteorological Institute (IPMA, Instituto Português do Mar e Atmosfera), located in Porto Santo Island. EEM receives in operation manner in its servers several products and here was used the Precipitation Accumulated product in 10 minutes time resolution (accumulated);
- ii) Numerical prediction model, WRF (Weather Research and Forecasting Model) which is operational in EEM servers and configured with ECMWF (European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts) data. This model runs for two daily cycles (00h and 12h) and 7 days horizon at 1km of horizontal resolution. From this model Accumulated Precipitation in 10 min is provided for a large area simulated (130x130 km²) and this field is intersected with each catchment area of hydro system in analysis;
- iii) EEM SCADA, responsible by control and record data measured in several points of the electrical grid.

The proposed methodology is based on predicting water availability for hydroelectric energy production. This requires making an initial estimation of the amount of water flowing into the hydro circuits based on rainfall data from different catchment areas and the accompanying inflows: Calheta III, Socorridos and Serra d'Água.

Fig. 2. Relation between Inflows and Catchment Areas

Calheta III (CTIII) receives water from nine sources, which derive from “levadas”, traditional irrigation canals that have been used for centuries to convey water for human consumption and agriculture. The Socorridos plant gets inflows primarily from two sources: a group of 17 canals in the Serra d'Água region (see Fig. 3) and two in Levada Fajã Rodrigues. In total, this implies six separate predictions using the proposed model.

Fig. 3. Serra d'Água catchment area divided by 17 separate zones

In order to create precise predictive simulations, data was systematically gathered at 10-minute intervals throughout an

entire year for each catchment. This high-resolution dataset was used as the basis for training our LSTM neural network models, with the goal of improving the accuracy of hydroelectric power generation estimates in the region.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The diversified dataset collected from different catchment regions around Madeira Island was applied to the proposed methodology. Before undergoing data processing, the output data needed to be prepared for training. This was necessary since the data was captured every minute, unlike the previous data sets which had ten-minute intervals. This meant selecting data that represented those 10 minutes intervals. After performing this, the pre-processing phase utilized an IQR approach to handle data outliers, specifically designed to handle non-zero numbers while maintaining the accuracy of zero-flow circumstances. In addition, an artificial attribute was created by computing the moving average across a defined interval to include the past pattern of water flow, so improving the models' capacity to make predictions based on temporal relationships. The LSTM models underwent training, with hyperparameters adjusted to maximize performance for each distinct hydrological location. The data was partitioned into an 80/20 ratio, with 80% allocated for training and 20% allocated for testing. As for the number of Epochs and Batch Size, several attempts to train each model were made until the best result possible was achieved. The architectural designs exhibited variations, specifically in the type and schema of input features and concealed LSTM units, which corresponded to the unique attributes of the input data in different catchments. In order to clarify the capabilities of the models, two summary tables were created: Table I presents the data characteristics for each catchment, whereas Table II provides detailed information on the performance of the LSTM models.

TABLE I. DATA SUMMARIZING

Name	Mean	Median	Min	Max
Socorridos Fajã Rodrigues	0,36	0,32	-22,75	22,77
Serra d'Água	0,26	0,22	0	1,32
CTIII Paul Velho	0,20	0,16	0	1,86
CTIII Paul 1 e 2	0,16	-0,0017	-6	6
CTIII Rabaçal	29,94	29,76	0	40,27
CTIII Rocha Vermelha	31,16	0,44	24,46	47,17

TABLE II. RESULTS SUMMARIZING (BEST TO WORSE)

Name	N_Inputs	Batch Size	N_Epochs	RMSE Normalized
Socorridos Fajã Rodrigues	2	64	350	0,0976
CTIII Rabaçal	2	64	210	0,0986
Serra d'Água	17	32	230	0,0991
CTIII Rocha Vermelha	2	64	160	0,110
CTIII: Paul 1 e 2	1	64	150	0,127
CTIII: Paul Velho	2	32	100	0,165

As for the number of hidden units and neurons, since all models had almost the same data size, the value is around the same for all modules. For the number of neurons, the value varied between 101 and 103. As for the hidden units, initially all models were trained with one and after tested with up to 5. Since all the data was normalized prior to the training of each LSTM network, it is possible to compare the RMSE values directly, despite the fact that not all represent the same type of variable. Table II shows that the best results occur for Socorridos Fajã Rodrigues, with an RMSE of 0,0976. Figure 4 depicts the high level of accuracy provided by the model, as predicted values closely match the actual flow pattern, thus indicating that the model is able to successfully learn and reproduce the temporal dynamics of the dataset.

Fig. 4. Actual Vs Predicted Values of Socorridos Fajã Rodrigues

On the other hand, the model CTIII Paul Velho has the least accurate result with an RMSE of 0,165. The model has a good performance following the general pattern of the water flow, as seen in Figure 5, which is quite similar to the actual data. However, it appears to lack accuracy predicting some of the most extreme spikes in values, which can be critical for operational decision-making in hydropower systems. These differences show that the model has difficulty in identifying extreme water flow outputs, introducing a smoothing effect. There are a number of reasons for this to happen. LSTM networks have a propensity to generalize, which means they might miss the sudden, fleeting changes that are characteristic of hydrological events, even if they can store information over lengthy stretches. Also, while this data comes from actual sensor readings, it is still affected by human intervention, such as when the water route is closed, and the output records are null until it is reopened and a sudden burst of water flow occurs.

Fig. 5. Actual Vs Predicted Values of CTIII Paul Velho

Results in Serra d'Água are a representative example of some of the difficulties found when developing the model. Figure 6 shows a situation where human-made variables are relevant. A

comparison of the expected and observed normalized streamflow values is shown in the graph. Human intervention controlling restricting water flow, resulting in periods of no flow, a state that is not taken into consideration by the prediction model, presently assessing the inflow according to natural flows.

A clear indication of these interventions is the fact that actual data shows sudden zeros while the projections do not. There appears to be a big disparity between the expected and actual numbers, which indicates that the model is failing to account for these non-natural flow occurrences. The unexpected nature of these interventions makes this integration difficult, yet it is vital for models to be used in controlled systems where human impact is common.

Fig. 6. Actual Vs Predicted Values of Serra d'Água

V. CONCLUSION

The main objective of this research is to support the hydroelectric power generation dispatch of EEM, by accurately predicting water inflows and thus deciding the best moments to store, turbine and pump water. This study provides valuable insights that can assist the decision-making agents in making more informed decisions, as an accurate prediction of the water inflow at strategic points becomes available.

The proposed research was tested using data obtained from EEM. Even though the proposed methodology was tested in the Madeira case, it is possible to replicate this approach to any other hydro power plants and cascade systems by gathering similar data, *i.e.* rainfall in the vicinity of the water flow, areas of catchment and waterways network. This study investigated the application of machine learning and time series models. Data on rainfall was gathered from the closest areas to the reservoirs and combined with real-time data of the water inflows that will eventually reach the units to produce energy. The best model had an RMSE of 0,0976, which indicates that it is capable of predicting inflows reasonably using rainfall alone. However, it is clear that having other types of inputs may improve the prediction accuracy of the model (for instance more weather information). In the cases where water flow is controlled, for predictive models to accurately represent the operational context in which they are used, the data should include data specific to human interaction when training the model.

Future work could include examining the introduction of more variables to the model, seeking accuracy improvement, applying the devised methodology to other water systems and using a longer dataset. It would be particularly interesting to

attempt to anticipate sudden events in a more accurate way, either by fine-tuning the present model or by adding a separate "quick-event" model to adjust the results presented here.

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